

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B166
Date: 01 Feb 2006
Take Off: 11:05:22
Landing: 15:49:25
Flight Time: 4h44m03

Campaign: DABEX
Trials Instructions: Biomass Burning
Operating Area: Niamey to Kaduna Lake (Nigeria)

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	CCN / CVI	Paul James	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	Filters	Paola Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
10	SWS / SHIMS	Claire McConnell	University of Reading
11	AMS	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester
12	Wet Neph	Simon Osborne	Met Office
13	VACC / PAN / Bags	Jim McQuaid	University of Leeds
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Flight Track:

B166 Track 01-FEB-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b166

Date: 01 Feb 2006

Project: DABEX

Location: Fires Over Nigeria, 09 55'N, 005 30'E

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
093746		Position	0.00 kft	311	13'28.65N, 2'10.53E
105405		INU	0.77 kft	311	Set to Navigate
105938		ASPs	0.77 kft	031	Open
110522		T/O	1.0 kft	088	Niamey
110522	112125	Profile 1	1.4 - 18.0 kft	103	1000fpm
110929		Videos	5.0 kft	147	Start FFC & DFC
112126	113033	Profile 2	18.0 - 10.0 kft	144	1000 fpm
113034	114630	Run 1	10.0 kft	143	Change level
114744	120359	Run 1	9.0 kft	131	Back in layer
120359	120751	Profile 3	9.0 - 5.0 kft	130	
120751	122143	Run 2	5.0 kft	131	
122128		Event	5.0 kft	137	Peak in signals
122456		Event	3.4 kft	246	Plume
122547	123958	Run 3.1	3.4 - 3.3 kft	274	B-C, Q1008
123019		Event	3.4 kft	271	Plume
123708		Event	3.4 kft	271	Plume
124049	124634	Run 3.2	3.3 - 3.4 kft	000	C-D
124633		Event	3.4 kft	000	Fire to Left
124849	124929	Run 4.1	1.4 - 1.7 kft	089	500ft 120
124913		Hairpin 1	1.6 kft	157	500ft
124949	125016	Orbit 1	1.6 - 1.8 kft	011	40deg lft,120-270deg
125135	125244	Orbit 2	2.0 - 1.8 kft	346	1k' 40lft,340-084
125500	125555	Orbit 3	2.8 kft	263	2k' 40lft,270-
125614		Event	2.8 kft	265	Plume
125729		Videos	2.9 kft	005	Change tapes
125855	131234	Run 4.1	3.4 kft	076	D-E @ 3200'
125952		Event	3.4 kft	088	Fire left
130932		Event	3.4 kft	090	Peaks in signals
131325	131616	Run 4.2	3.4 kft	181	E-L
131616		Position			L @ 09 55'N,006 00'E
131707	133205	Run 4.3	3.4 kft	268	L-M
133205		Position			L @ 09 55'N,005 00'E
131932		Event	3.4 kft	269	Fires left
132645		Event	3.4 kft	270	Ovhd fire
133415	135003	Run 5.1	1.4 - 1.2 kft	090	500',3nm south M-L
135112	140754	Run 5.2	1.3 - 1.5 kft	273	1.5nm south L-M
140928	142556	Run 5.3	1.4 kft	075	0.8nm south M-L
142502		Videos	1.2 kft	091	Change tapes
142855	143009	Orbit 4	1.4 - 1.6 kft	267	Left 50deg
143009	143122	Orbit 5	1.7 - 1.6 kft	192	Left 50deg
143154	144309	Profile 4	1.9 - 12.0 kft	256	500fpm to FL50
144309	144814	Profile 5	12.0 - 8.0 kft	309	
144815	150935	Run 6	8.0 kft	310	
150936	151145	Profile 6	8.0 - 10.0 kft	310	1000fpm
151146	151334	Run 7	10.0 kft	310	1000fpm
151335	151438	Profile 7	10.0 - 9.1 kft	310	
151439	154050	Run 8	9.0 - 8.5 kft	309	
154050	154925	Profile 8	5.7 - 0.85 kft	319	FL85 to surface
154925		Land	0.84 kft	087	Niamey
155056		Heimann	0.84 kft	090	Shutter open
155213		INU	0.84 kft	269	Start Align, r/w 270
155955		INU	0.84 kft	269	To Navigate
160040		Event	0.85 kft	267	Start taxi r/w 270
160452		Event	0.86 kft	267	Stop taxi @ end r/w
160613		Event	0.86 kft	267	Start backtrack
160755		Event	0.86 kft	088	Exit r/w
161030		Position	0.86 kft	315	13'28.65N, 2'10.53E

B166 Track 01-FEB-06

RRN -> DBBB - Overview

avData Cycle 2006-1 Expires: Thursday, 16 February 2006.
Scale: 1:2288671 (1 inch = 31.39 naut mi). Printed on 01 Feb 2006

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.150

FAAM Sortie Brief

DABEX: sampling of fresh biomass burning plumes

Flight No: B166

Date: 1st February 2006

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling of biomass burning smoke close to sources and perform high level patterns for SHIMS and SWS calibrations.

Location:

Over land areas in the regions of Point A (9°10'N, 6°E), Point B (9°40'N, 6°E), Point C(9°40'N, 5°E), Point D (10°10'N, 5°E), Point E (10°10'N, 6°E), Point F (10°40'N, 6°E), Point G (10°40'N, 5°E), Point H (11°10'N, 5°E), Point I(11°10'N, 5°E), Point J (11°40'N, 6°E), Point K (11°40'N, 5°E), and in the region of Niamey.

Weather:

High loadings of biomass burning aerosol. Cloudless skies preferred. Cloudless skies essential for end of sortie (calibrations).

Special requirements:

Low-level (500ft) flying over land.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Niamey.
2. Profile ascent from 2300ft to FL180 at 1000ft/min towards point A [15 mins, T=15mins]
3. Profile descent to FL080 towards Point B [10mins, 25mins]
4. SLR at FL080 towards Point B [40 mins, T=65mins]
5. Profile descent to point B at 3200ft [5 mins, T=70 mins]
6. SLR at 3200ft from point B to point C [15 mins, T=85mins]
7. SLR at 3200ft from point C to point D [8 mins, T=93mins]
8. SLR at 3200ft from point D to point E [15 mins, T=108 mins]
9. SLR at 3200ft from point E to point F [8 mins, T=116 mins]
10. SLR at 3200ft from point F to point G [15 mins, T=131 mins]
11. SLR at 4000ft from point G to point H [8 mins, T=138 mins]
12. SLR at 4000ft from point H to point I [15 mins, T=153 mins]
13. SLR at 4000ft from point I to point J [8 mins, T=161 mins]
14. SLR at 4000ft from point J to point K [15 mins, T=176 mins]
15. Profile ascent towards Niamey from 3000ft to FL050 at 1000ft/min [4 mins, T=180mins].
16. SLR at FL050 towards Niamey [25 mins, T=205mins]
17. Broken profile ascent from FL050 to FL180 at 1000ft/min in vicinity of Niamey [15mins, T=220 mins]
18. Box pattern at FL180 consisting of 5 min legs orientated into, across, down and across sun [25mins, T=245 mins]
19. A series of four orbits at FL200, at maximum bank angle, two LH and two RH turns [10mins, T=255 mins]
20. Profile descent from FL200 to ~2000ft at 1000ft/min [20mins, T=275mins]
21. Land Niamey.

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B166

Date: 1st February 2006

Sortie Objectives: DABEX flight to investigate the in-situ properties and radiative properties of fresh biomass burning.

Operating area: Nigeria between the following points

Point B (9°40'N , 6°E)

Point C (9°40'N , 5°E)

Point D (10°10'N , 5°E)

Point E (10°10'N , 6°E)

Point J (11°40'N , 6°E)

Point K (11°40'N , 5°E)

Weather: Completely free from cirrus for the whole flight. Hazy conditions (mainly mineral dust at low levels, with some overlying biomass burning aerosols in the Niamey region. Smokey/mineral dust aerosols in the Nigeria operating region.

Flight Patterns: Take off from Niamey was followed by a profile ascent from the ground to FL180, which was completely free from aerosol. A layer of mineral dust was observed from the surface to 3500ft, followed by a small distinct biomass burning layer at FL50, and a broader biomass burning layer from FL70 to FL120. A SLR for approximately 30mins was then performed at FL100 in the direction of the Nigerian operating area, but the stratification of the aerosol layer changed significantly, and so the SLR was adjusted to FL90. A profile descent was then performed to FL50 where a 15minute SLR was performed heading towards point B. Heavy concentrations of large particles were observed at FL50 with the nephelometer scattering reaching $\sim 700 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$. A message came through from OPS informing us of the position of the fires from the MODIS rapidfire imagery, which was available some 2hours after TERRA satellite overpass. The imagery suggested that the most significant burning was to the south of the proposed B-C-K-J operating region. We then repositioned to point B and moved to the MPA, which was 3200ft (on QNH 1008mb \sim FL34) where some burning was observed. A run from B to C was then performed, high concentrations of aerosol were observed – heavy smoke. Just before point D, some moderate fires were observed to the LHS of the aircraft and the run was broken off to perform some in situ sampling of the fresh plumes. This involved a couple of hairpin manoeuvres which are particle orbits to get the radiance as a function of scattering angle in 3 half orbits, and some SLRs at 500ft AGL. Subsequently the aircraft repositioned to point D and the aircraft performed a SLR from point D to point E. Moderate/large fires were observed on the RHS, and we therefore subdivide the B-C-D-E box and performed a series of 4 15-minute runs in east-west direction, the first at FL32, and the last three at 500ft AGL. Heavy concentrations of smoke were observed along all of these legs with some very well defined plumes. Two 50degree orbits were then performed away from the plumes, before a profile ascent that took the aircraft back towards Niamey. An approximately AOD calculation suggest that the AOD was 1.5, and the difference between the green, red and blue scattering was not very large suggesting large particles. The aircraft was close to its minimum fuel reserves, so not

much manoeuvring was possible on the way back to Niamey, with SLRs at FL100, and FL90, which were periodically in the biomass burning layer. A profile descent (dirty) was then performed to landing.

Summary: Brilliant! We have got some unique data here. Not sure why the aerosol particles are so large – either mineral dust or fly ash seem the most likely explanations. The low level 500ft runs should give the spectral surface radiative forcing. The in-situ data will be extremely interesting.

Problems:

One or two times when the SWS and SHIMS were only working with visible modules.

Jim Haywood

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B166**
~~B165-2~~

Date 30th Jan 2000

Page 1 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Hazy, ci clearing in morning.
					Visibility 4km. DUST reported on TRAB & METARS.
13:10:23		T/O 500ft	Niamey	#134	Dust top ~ FL50 to surface. Some evidence of local dust plume production: - in neph data.
	ST RA				
13:36:27	End RA	500ft		#135	Good run! No Ci overhead. BBRS ~ 770 Wm ⁻² .
13:39:26	ST P16	500ft ↑		#135	
13:51					1/8 Ci only.
13:51:53	End P16	FL150		#134	SWS looking ↓ nadir. (SWSN) SHIMS may have a very little Ci contamination.
13:56:16	ST R10	FL150		#134	4,500m in dust reported by Niamey.
14:07:38	End R10	FL150		#135	A little Ci → check ratio of upper red / upper red dome.
14:10:21	ST R11	FL150		#137	— 11 — Same variability of ~ ± 20 Wm ⁻²
14:21:06	End R11			#136	
14:25:18	ST P17	FL150 ↓		#136	V. little Ci, but some effect on the BBRs.
14:37:44	End P17	500ft		#137	

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**.....166.....

Date30 Jan 2009.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:40:32	St R12	500ft	137 →136	13.6, 2.7E	Very hazy above
					SID suggests many non-spherical particles
					~ 6000ft AGL.
14:44					PCASP 300-400 cm ⁻³
					Neph green > neph red & blue
14:54:23	End R12	500ft	136	13.6, 1.9E	
14:59:23	St R13	500ft	142 → 143		
15:12:33	End R13				
15:15:43	St P18	500ft		13.3, 2.7E	Birds at 6000ft.
					Climbing out of aerosol at 6000ft. AOD ≈ 0.6.
15:28:06	End P18	FL150			Stuck due to ATC problems.
15:35:46	St R14	FL150			Ci cloud increasing to 6'8. No paint in SW rats with this cloud. ∴ Change to in-situ sampling & land.
	St R15	FL110		143 → 142	

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...166.....**

Date **1st Feb 2006..**

Page **1** of **.....**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					No cirrus.
					Hazy, windier than all previous days ≈ 0.4 . (total microtops)
11:05:22	St P1				T/O Niamey.
					Hazy visibility ~ 6 km.
					Clear slot @ 5300ft (visual)
					Deepish layer of dust (visual).
					Ci free.
					FL20
					Z (FL) ← BB
					FL70
					FL50 ← BB
					FL35
					Dust
					50 Green 300 Scm $\times 10^{-6} (\text{m}^{-3})$
11:21:26	End P1	FL180		12.6N, 2.9E	Lower dust layer to FL35
"	St P2				BB layer at FL50
					BB layer peak at FL100
11:30:34	End P2 St R1	FL100		17.0, 3.3	
					A little closer to top of BB layer. — very aged BB or even dust.
11:46:13	Int R1	FL60			
11:47:44	Restart R1	FL90		11.1, 2.4E	Higher concentrations lower down. PLASF 800 cm^{-3}
12:03:59	End R1 St P3	FL90		10.4, 5.1	
12:07:51	End St R2	FL50			Large dust concentrations.

Mission Scientist's Log

10:30
D+E.

Flight No **B**...166.....

Date ...1st Feb 2006.....

Page ...2 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:19					In heavy dust sea = $700 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^{-1}$
12:20					CO + SID increase → over plane.
12:21:43	End R2	5000ft ↓			Reposition to point B.
12:25:47	St R3.1	3200ft			Some BB plumes here at point B.
12:29:50	End R3.1	3200ft		C → D	
12:40:49	St R3.2	3200ft.		C → D	
12:44.					Interface between forest/usable land.
12:46:34	End R3.2				Fires here!
					Hairpin manoeuvres. Partial orbits.
					All hell broke loose through large fires. Orbits at 45° (partial).
12:58:55	St 4.1	3200ft		D → E	Some small plumes on RHS. Some BB peaks.
13:12:34	St 4.1	"		E → L	Turn towards Bravo to now, new point Leema 1/2 way between B & B.
13:13:25	St 4.2			L	
13:16:16	End 4.2				
13:17:07	St R 4.2			L → M	Fires on RHS

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....166.....

Date 1st Feb 2006.....

Page 3 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:32:05	End R4.3	3200ft			Dust with BB phones popping through.
13:34:15	St R5.1	500ft			Lots of fresh smoke, mixed with mineral dust.
13:50:03	End R5.1	500ft			Lots of smoke
13:51:12	St R5.2	500ft			Mineral dust etc.
14:07:54	End R5.2	500ft			Vegetation a mix of scrub/forest interspersed with
14:09:28	St R5.3	"			Horace Miss sci crash.
14:25:56	End R5.3	"			Good orbits.
	St 01				50° angle of bank.
	End 01				
	Stop				
	End 02				
14:31:54	St P4	1000ft			
14:43:09	End P4 St P5	FL120			Profile descent
14:48:15	End P5 St R6	FL80			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B166

Date : 01 Feb 2006

Operator and contact info : Doug Anderson (dougan@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	Post ground to aircraft power switch problem meant CO didn't restart until another switch off/on carried out during taxi. CO not online until part way along the runway during take-off @ ~ 11:05:20. Previous ground cal therefore not particularly useful for profile 1 starting from take-off.
O₃	Very noisy while at low level (500') between 14:16 and 14:44. ALARM during that period Intensity B HIGH. Increase in altitude to FL120 seemed to fix problem which started again as we returned to FL080 @ 14:49. ALARM now Bench Temp HIGH & Intensity B HIGH. O3 switched off 15:11:20 to allow cooling down. Rebooted 15:25:15. No ALARMS now and signal now seems OK.
NO_x	None. Noticeable lag on HORACE display between O3 and NOx peaks while passing through sharp smoke plumes.
SO₂	None
TDLAS	Not operated
WAS	Not operated

CO Calibrations

A full calibration lasts approx three minutes, it consists of a cal and a zero
Shorter (quick cal) are sometimes done at low level which is calibration only

<u>Time (GMT)</u>	<u>Level</u>	<u>Comments</u>
10:31:46	Ground	
11:33:19	FL100	
11:51:07	FL090	
12:10:44	FL050	
12:29:13	3200'	
12:42:50	3200'	
		Several level changes down to 500' without cals as we went through smoke plumes between end of R3.2 and start of R4.1. CO peaks above 2000ppb several times, one above 9000ppb. Some of these values are almost certainly due to flying through our own exhaust.
13:01:47	3200'	
13:37:29	500'	
14:11:10	500'	
14:56:04	FL080	O3 alarms for Bench temp (43.2, Max set to 43.0) and Intensity B (not noted) both high.
15:18:00	FL090	

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF		1	2	3	4	5	
		25.69	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
113034	100	25.69	0.16	0.29	0.48	0.68	1.03	S
		24.49	100	829	808	1287	1623	D
		23.02	217	204	245	245	322	B
		22.2	2361	2361	2386	2388	240	R
		21.84	977.7	977.7	977.7	977.7	977.7	P
		25.3	0.16	0.29	0.46	0.68	1.00	S
		24.02	600	873	1299	1400	2000	D
		23.87	212	219	219	247	476	B
		23.04	2506	2510	2511	2509	2504	R
114740	040	22.5	984	984	984	984	984	P
			1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		25.71	0.16	0.29	0.47	0.68	1.03	S
120751	Run 2 050	24.65	733	1197	1876	2315	3622	D
		23.82	218	222	222	260	316	B
		23.11	2475	2470	2465	2466	2463	R
		21.95	986	986.4	986.4	986.4	986.4	P
		25.66	0.16	0.29	0.46	0.67	1.02	S
122547	032	24.73	1727	2678	3502	4092	4092	D
		23.95	288	298	349	349	585	B
		23.52	2438	2435	2428	2425	2425	R
		22.5	981.7	981.7	981.7	981.7	981.7	P
			1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		25.94	0.16	0.31	0.48	0.69	1.06	S
1243	032	25.41	1302	2175	3239	3883	4092	D
	001	24.07	279	283	283	333	322	B
		24	2358	2362	2363	2362	2364	R
125855		22.20	981.7	981.5	981.5	981.5	981.5	P
		26.12	0.16	0.30	0.45	0.69	1.06	S
131325		25.82	1500	2724	4092	4092	4092	D
		24.64	297	299	344	344	344	B
		23.79	2424	2458	2471	2486	2486	R
			981.8	981.8	981.8	981.8	981.8	P
			1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
133415		26.39	0.16	0.30	0.47	0.69	1.06	S
		25.23	1881	2058	2787	3333	4092	D
		24.43	251	271	306	306	627	B
		23.97	2365	2359	2350	2353	2358	R
		22.95	981.7	981.7	981.7	981.7	981.7	P
		26.24	0.16	0.30	0.47	0.69	1.05	S
135112		25.74	2083	3489	4023	4092	4092	D
		24.85	267	267	305	305	397	B
		24.18	2314	2515	2817	2506	2695	R
		23.08	981.8	981.2	981.2	981.2	981.9	P

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B166

Date:

01 FEB 2006

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet	90 mm 0.4 µm Nuclepore followed by a 90 mm paper (top)
Except for				

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B166Q4	----	----	Top	11:30:34	12:03:59	R1	3066	FL100, old biomass, dropped 1000 feet half way through (quartz filter found broken)
Filters run1	B166N4	----	----	Bottom	11:30:34	12:03:59	R1	2037	FL100, old biomass, dropped 1000 feet half way through
Filters run2	B166Q5	----	----	Top	12:07:51	12:21:43	R2	1521	5000 feet, dust
Filters run2	B166N5	----	----	Bottom	12:07:51	12:21:43	R2	1134	5000 feet, dust
Filters run3	B166Q6	----	----	Top	12:26:00	12:39:58	R3.1	1663	3300-3400 feet, smoke plumes at 12:30:19 and 12:37:08
Filters run3	B166N6	----	----	Bottom	12:26:00	12:39:58	R3.1	1248	3300-3400 feet, smoke plumes at 12:30:19 and 12:37:08
Filters run4	B166Q7	----	----	Top	12:53:00	12:58:00		486	2800 feet, smoke plume at 12:56:14
Filters run4	B166N7	----	----	Bottom	12:53:00	12:58:00		476	2800 feet, smoke plume at 12:56:14
Filters run5	B166Q8	----	----	Top	13:34:00	13:50:03	R5.1	1647	1200-1400 feet, fresh smoke
Filters run5	B166N8	----	----	Bottom	13:34:00	13:50:03	R5.1	1407	1200-1400 feet, fresh smoke
Filters run6	B166Q9	----	----	Top	13:55:00	14:07:34	R5.2	1355	1300-1500 feet, fresh smoke
Filters run6	B166N9	----	----	Bottom	13:55:00	14:07:34	R5.2	1068	1300-1500 feet, fresh smoke
Filters run7	B166Q10	----	----	Top	14:11:00	14:26:00	R5.3	1548	1400 feet, fresh smoke
Filters run7	B166N10	----	----	Bottom	14:11:00	14:26:00	R5.3	1315	1400 feet, fresh smoke
Filters run8	B166Q11	----	----	Top	14:48:15	15:09:36	R6	1888	FL080, old biomass
Filters run8	B166N11	----	----	Bottom	14:48:15	15:09:36	R6	1521	FL080, old biomass

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B.166**.....

Date ..**0.1/02/06**..

Operator's name: **DS Borne**.....

Page**1** of **6**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
			<u>18 lpm</u>					PRE-FLIGHT CHECKS → NEPH ZERO.
	Dry neph	zero.	360s pulse time ; Good 2.2%.		300s zero period itself.			T _{air} = 296.6 K, T _{sample} = 297.2 K
	Wet Neph	→	using dry neph zero flow with valve set to open, no zero lags etc (but a little noisy)					
	Wet neph zero		360s pulse ; 300s zero period. Didn't seem to work - try again					↳ running in a zero mode afterwards
	(after 1hr)	Dry neph		T _{inlet} = 299.5 K, T _{sample} = 300.7 K - (OK) v. high values.				
	WET NEPH	zero	(2 nd attempt)					v. noisy and 'wandering'. Strange.
	Duffa Neph	talking to CABVIEW						will not try chiller!! w _g ~ 0.82
				RH = 10.9%	10.6%	37.4%	RH3 = 10.3%	RH5 = 31.1%
				Good!!				OK
								Neph1 (DRY) on for 10 mins.
11:15				NO WATER IN CHILLER				After 10 mins recording still to CABVIEW. Chiller not can COMS no set-up.
	(NB)			wet neph air sample was passed thru empty humidifier which is vented to outside!!				
			FL450	start climb				Both neph ~ zero with some -ve values.
11:23	P2	P200	9.3	0.5%	44%			
11:31	R1	FL100	10.8	12%	39%			No water in chiller. w _g ~ 0.54.
11:35	R1	FL100			34%		24°C	Water in chiller. Temp. dropping. FL46 dropping too!!

↳ Set to +5°C.

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B**.....166.....

Date ...01/02/06...

Operator's name: ...D.S. BARNIE.....

Page ...2 of ...6...

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
113930	R1	R2100	10	12%	28%	↓	12.8°C	RH wet low enough to start - run.
114030	R1					↗	25°C	→ set to this temp.
114130	R1	R2100	10	14	34		25°C	Now.
114300								check drain trap by opening - blip on RH sensors.
114400								back to normal.
114443	R1	R2000	10	14%	40%	↗	30°C	Set.
114621				16%	44%		30°C	reached.
114743	R1	R2090						Re-start.
114905	R1	R2090	10.0	16%			35°C	Set
114949	R1	R2090	10	16%	50.6%	↗	35°C	Reached. (RH5 = 63%) ^(drop) Big change RH5 → RH6.
115132	R1	R2090	10.1				40°C	Set
115224				17%	62%	↗	40°C	Reached. (RH5 = 84%) ↗ increasing!! RH 0.55 → 0.65, MAY TEMP. AS SET.
115344	R1	R2090	10.2			↗	45°C	
115503	R1	R2090	10.1	14.8%	73.6%	→	45°C	Reached. (RH5) ambient (dry) signal vanishes alt. RH5 = 93%.
				15.8	77%	→		Moisture = wet neph.
115742	R1	R2090	10.3			↓	20°C	Set for drop.
115830								RH5 dropping fairly quickly.

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B**.....166.....

Date ...07/02/06.....

Operator's name: ...OSBORN.....

Page ...3... of ...6...

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
11595				14.8	60.8	↓	32°C	RH5 ≈ RH6 during ramp down.
1203				17	44%	↓	24°C	RH5 = 35%.
120345	R1	end R090				↓	10°C	Set 50 us to start new ramp at wet level & profile down to F200. Leave pump on.
(12057)	←							
120920	R2	F2050					25°C	Set.
121300	R2	F2050	10.1	12%	37%	↗	30°C	Set. In dust (+BIOMASS?) LAZOR
121500	R2	F2050	10.2	12	42	↗	35°C	Set.
121700	R2	F2050	10.1	12.5	51	↗	40°C	Set. v. responsive humidity! GREAT!
122000				12.9	58	→	40°C	T _{in} = 27.7°C.
122110		F2050					45°C	Set. MAX H ₂ O temp.
12225				16	76			R w/s in 1-1 B.S. hit on ground → lots of biomass plumes about.
122935	R3.1	5200'	10.7	14		↓	15°C	Set RH5 = 76%, RH6 = 74%. RH in wet rept less responsive than. RH5 sensor Air volume change problem.
123647		3200'	10.7	13	40		30°C	Set (from 21°C) RH5 ≈ 24% 30%
123725	R3.1	3200'		12.5	45		35°C	Set.
123959	R3.1	3200'						End run.
124000	R3.2	3200'		13.5	51		40°C	Set RH5 = 48.5%
		1000' AGL	10%	12	70		45°C	Set to MAX. plume hunting

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B**.....166.....

Date ..01/02/06.....

Operator's name: ...OSBORNE.....

 Page 4 of 6.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
1254		2000'	10.0	13%	73%			T _{air} = 31.4°C RH5 = 77.7%
125630								Good plume hit w/ up to 103 m @ 550m
130000		3200'	9.7	12.5	70	↓	15°C	SBT ramp down during warm up.
130910	R4.1	3200'	9.9	12.2	34	↗	25°C	SEA start new ramp up.
131200	R4.1	3200'	9.8	12.5	37	↗	30°C	SEA ramping up.
131416	R4.2	3200'	9.7	13	42	↗	35°C	SEA
131710	R4.3	3200'	9.8	14	52	↗	40°C	SEA set at very start of R4.3
								Growth seen 50-60% RH wet.
131900	R4.3	3200'	9.9	13	57		45°C	SEA set to max. Natural variation over whole run.
			9.8	11	70			Max RH wet here ~ 70% humidity.
								T _{air} = 32.2°C. Add more H ₂ O for a while.
132500		3200'		11	71	↓	15°C	SEA.
								RAMP DOWN shows v. LITTLE change - 70%
		500' ASL	10.2	10.3	33%	↘	20°C	Base of ramp.
133416	R5.1	"				↗	30°C	Start ramp up at start of run "soft side"
133615	R5.1	500' ASL	10.0			↗	35°C	SEA.
133810	R5.1	500' ASL	10.4	12	43	↗	40°C	SEA
134015	R5.1	500' ASL	10.4	11	53	↗	45°C	SEA set to max. H ₂ O temp. T _{air} = 33°C
134400	"	"	10.4	11.9	63			Max RH? No growth seen.

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B**.....166.....

Date ..01/02/06.....

Operator's name: ...OSBORNE.....

Page 5... of ..6..

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
134550	RS.1	500 ft	10.2	11.9 13	63 30	↘	15°C	SET RH5 = 68% struggling to get to high getting low RH is not a problem!!
135610	RS.2	500 ft	10.2	11	26(!!)	↗	30°C	RAMP UP
140100	"	"	10.3	8.3	32	↗	35°C	" "
140230	"	"	10.2	9.6	40	↗	40°C	" "
140450	"	"	10.1	9.3	49	↗	45°C	" " to MAX T _{in} = 35°C !!
161030	RS.3	500 ft	10.2	9.0	60.2			manipulations show no growth ⇒ leave on (T _{in} = 35-20°C) (RH5 = 70%) MAX temp for neptun
141700	RS.3	500 ft	10.2	9.6	60.4	↓	15°C	SET RAMP DOWN.
1418								Good plume: nice structure of dry neph.
14152						↗	45°C	SET TO MAX RH _{wet} < 20% after a long time at T ₄₂₀ = 15°C.
141430								open trap valve briefly → NO WATER AS ALL → survived profiles, orbits etc!!
145052	R3	FL800	9.7	9.6	70%	↘	20°C	set for ramp down
145300		FL800	12.09	Increase flow	as a test			No leak
145440		FL800	14.3	"	"	"	"	No leak
145640		FL800	16.0	"	"	"	"	No leak
145835		FL800	16	9.9	26	↗	39°C	RAMP UP.
145940		FL800	12.0	set as a safe flow	(sample) rate			
150225		FL800	12.0	9.9	42	↗	45°C	set further ramp to MAX temp.

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B**...166.....

Date ...01/02/06...

Operator's name: ...OSBORNE.....

Page 6... of 6...

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
154			11.2	7%	60%	→	65°C	Profile ascent from FL080 → FL090 to get within chiller around.
151615		FL090	12.3	7.5%	60%	↘	25°C	RAMP DOWN.
152240		FL090	12.2	8.3	26	↗	65°C	RAMP UP. within EPL (60 mins burning) T _{in} = 33.8°C. A little cooler up here.
152645		FL090	12.3	5.7%	58%	↘	20°C	→ set to RAMP DOWN. ↳ pretty poor as an upper limit!!
153300		FL090	12.4	6.3	29.5%	↘	~23°C	Switch down system at end of ramp down. ↳ chiller OFF → wet cell OFF. leave DRY cell ON now (to get temperature of DRY).
153531	FB	↳	LABVIEW	↳	↳			

PC

+ SHIMS

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 166	Date	1/2/06	Operator(s)	CLAIRE MCCONNELL	log page	1 of 3
Time	Run Id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

PC

SHIMS

						Preflight data - problems w/ initialization of SHIMS (T too low).
			N/A			
10:52			BE	100ms	350ms	Recording. Both modules OK. Dark
			BE	75ms	350ms	
10:55:15	T/O					
11:06:11	P1		BE	75ms	350ms	Time as in Flight Summary
11:09:14	P1					End Recording
	P1					Dark
11:09:57	P1		BE	75	250	Changed Int. times.
						Dark
11:21:41	P2			75	250	
11:30:33	P2					End P2
11:36:42						Dark
11:31:03	R1	FL100				Rec
11:42:58	R1			75	250	End R1 Dark
11:43:12	R1			50	250	Dark
11:43:30	R1			50	250	Start & Recording
11:46:38						Rec Dark
11:47:05				"	"	Recording
11:47:44	R1			"	"	Run Resumed
12:03:59	R1			"	"	End R1
12:03:59	P3			"	"	Start P3
12:07:51	R2	FL050		"	"	Start R2
12:11:06	R2			"	"	Stop Rec
12:11:13	R2			"	"	Dark
12:11:25	R2			"	"	Rec
12:15:34						Stop Rec - no signal
12:15:50						Dark
12:16:06						Rec - no signal
						Restart Labview
12:31	R3			50	250	Dark vis only
12:32	R3			"	"	Rec
				"	"	Interrupt Run
12:40:05				"	"	Dark
12:40:25	R3.2			"	"	Rec
12:46:34	R3.2			"	"	Interrupt Run
12:48:49	R4.1			"	"	
14:19:13	Hair 1			"	"	
12:49:49	O1			"	"	

+ SHIMS

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B/C	Date	1/2/06	Operator(s)	C. MCCONNELL	log page	7	of	3
Time	Run Id	Alt/FL	Mirt Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

PC SHIMS
↓

Time	Run Id	Alt/FL	Mirt Pos	Vis	NIR	Remarks
12:51:35	02			MS 50	MS 250	
12:58:55	R4-1					
12:59:27	R4-1					Dark
12:59:47	R4-1					Rec (D → E)
13:05:19						Stop Rec
13:07:20	R4-1			50	250	Dark
13:07:32	R4-1			"	"	Rec - VIS end NIR now
13:09:16	R4-1			50	200	Dark
13:09:25	R4-1			"	"	Rec
13:12:36	R4-1					End Run
13:13:25	R4-2					E → L
13:16:16	R4-2					End Run
13:17:07	R4-3					L → M
13:21:19	R4-3					Dark
13:24:30	R4-3					Rec
13:32:05	R4-3					End Run
13:36:15	R5-1					Start Run
13:49:29	R5-1					Dark
13:49:39	R5-1					Rec
13:50:03	R5-1					End Run
13:51:12	R5-2			"	"	Start Run
14:07:54	R5-2					End Run
14:08:05						Dark
14:08:19						Rec
14:23	R5-3					Stop
14:25			60	30	250	Dark
14:26:02				"	"	Rec
14:28:55	04					Start Orbit - VIS IR over top
14:30:09	04					End Orbit at times
14:30:21	05					Start Orbit - VIS IR over top
14:31:22	05					End Orbit at times
14:31:54	P4					
14:34						Stop Rec
14:36:09				50	200	Dark
14:36:40	P4					Rec
14:43:09	P4					End P4
14:43:09	15					Start Profile
14:48:15	R6-1	FLO80				Start Run

SWS
↓

SHIMS
↓

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 166	Date	1/2/06	Operator(s)	C. MCCONNELL	log page	1 of 2
Time	Run Id	Alt/FL	Mtr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

↓ Times are PC on rack times

LAPTOP
SWS

11:21:20

~11:16	P1		6°	100	350	Recording started after T/O.	
11:17:08	P1			75	350	Dark	
11:18:00	P1			75	350		
				150	350	Dark	
11:19	P1			150	350		
						Dark	
11:21	P1			200			
11:23:00	P2			"		Start profile	
11:23:00	P2			"		Dark	
11:23:37	P2			"		Recording	
11:30:33	P2					End P2	
11:30:34	R1	FL100				Start R1	
11:33:47	R1					Dark	
11:34:07	R1					Recording	
11:44:55	R1			150 ²⁰⁰		Dark	
11:45:20	R1			150		Dark	
11:45:27	R1			150		Recording	
11:50:44	R1	FL090		"		Laptop PC Reset to PC time	
12:06:30						Rec stopped	
12:06:46						Dark	
				75		Dark	
12:07:27	R2			75		Recording	
12:29						Dark	
12:30						Rec - no signal	
12:31						Signal back	
12:40:15						Stop Rec	
12:41:01						Dark	
12:41:17	R3.2					Rec	
12:47:19						Stop Rec	
				50		Dark	
12:48:02				"		Rec	
12:49						Vis occasionally over top.	
12:50:17				30		Dark	
12:50:34				30		Rec	
12:58:55	R4.1					Start R4.1	
13:10:58	R4.1					Dark	
13:11:13	R4.1					Rec	
13:25:10	R4.1					Dark	
13:25:22	R4.1		6°			Rec	
13:50:10	R5.1					Dark	
13:50:23	R5.1					Rec	

Bags are numbers 1-140 and tubes are the other samples

Date	01/02/06	Tubes & Bags		Flight#	B166
T.O.	11:05:22	Land	15:49:33		Jim McQuaid (ULeeds)
Tube/Bag #	START	END	Alt. (ft)	Sample Time	Comments
000100	12:19:30	12:21:10		00:01:40	
000015	12:21:28	12:23:30		00:02:02	
000016	12:27:00	12:28:10	3200	00:01:10	16 underlined
067639	12:29:00	12:34:50		00:05:50	067839???
000012	12:35:30	12:37:30		00:02:00	
000132	12:37:40	12:38:40		00:01:00	
067342	12:52:00	12:55:30		00:03:30	
000139	12:39:00	12:40:30		00:01:30	
062342	12:37:00	12:51:30	BLANK	00:14:30	BLANK
000125	12:48:20	12:50:00		00:01:40	
000033	12:50:20	12:51:30		00:01:10	
000079	12:55:40	12:56:30		00:00:50	
000129	12:58:00	12:59:50		00:01:50	
000105	13:00:10	13:02:00		00:01:50	
051541	13:07:00	13:13:50		00:06:50	
000017	13:14:00	13:15:30		00:01:30	
067699	13:20:40	13:27:10		00:06:30	
000124	13:16:10	13:17:50		00:01:40	
000121	13:18:50	13:20:30		00:01:40	
000006	13:28:35	13:30:10		00:01:35	
000013	13:30:20	13:32:40		00:02:20	
000086	13:34:30	13:36:35		00:02:05	
000119	13:36:45	13:38:20		00:01:35	
067652	13:38:20	13:46:40		00:08:20	
000003	13:48:40	13:50:00		00:01:20	
000014	13:50:10	13:51:50		00:01:40	
000040	13:53:20	13:54:50		00:01:30	
067662	13:55:00	14:02:30		00:07:30	
000080	14:02:40	14:03:40		00:01:00	
000117	14:04:10	14:06:00		00:01:50	
067607	14:07:10	14:13:10	500	00:06:00	
000112	14:13:30	14:14:55	500	00:01:25	
000113	14:15:00	14:17:00	500	00:02:00	
000118	14:17:10	14:19:00	500	00:01:50	
062306	14:19:20	14:24:00	500	00:04:40	
000107	14:24:20	14:26:10	500	00:01:50	
000070	14:26:35	14:28:20	500	00:01:45	
000120	14:31:30	14:33:30	500	00:02:00	
000115	14:33:40	14:35:50	500	00:02:10	
000111	14:36:10	14:37:20	500	00:01:10	
000035	14:37:30	14:38:20	500	00:00:50	
000116	14:38:30	14:39:30	500	00:01:00	
000109	14:39:40	14:40:45	500	00:01:05	
000039	14:40:50	14:41:55	500	00:01:05	
000126	14:42:00	14:43:10	500	00:01:10	
000032	14:43:30	14:44:50	500	00:01:20	
067893	14:52:30	15:00:45		00:08:15	
000053	15:01:20	15:02:20		00:01:00	
000101	15:02:30	15:03:30		00:01:00	
000122	15:04:10	15:05:00		00:00:50	122*
062327	15:07:20	15:15:00		00:07:40	
062131	15:20:10	15:25:00	9000	00:04:50	
000048	15:25:30	15:26:30	9000	00:01:00	
000084	15:28:15	15:29:55	9000	00:01:40	
000135	15:30:20	15:33:20	9000	00:03:00	
062173	15:35:00	15:41:00	9000	00:06:00	

MICROTOPS II SUNPHOTOMETER SHEET NO

DATE 1st Feb 2006 SKY CONDITIONS
 OPERATOR Paul Gerard FILENAME ONCE DOWNLOADED
 START TIME

Enter Site Details Below:

Site Name in Full Niway Abbreviate NIM
 Latitude Longitude Height above sea level(m)

AOD

TIME	SKY	SITE	MTP Scan Number	AOD (380)	AOD(440)	AOD(675)	AOD(936)	AOD (1020)	WV(g/cm ²)
07:11:09	1	NIM		0.508	0.466	0.383	0.347	0.299	1.00
08:26:33	1	"	86	0.466	0.428	0.354	0.311	0.268	1.07
09:29:29	1	NIM		0.505	0.469	0.393	0.349	0.301	1.11
10:40:04	1		131	0.462	0.431	0.361	0.318	0.274	1.09
11:32:37	1	"	132	0.445	0.425	0.383	0.351	0.302	1.04
12:01:37	1	"	133	0.483	0.453	0.388	0.363	0.313	1.03
12:31:47	1	"	136	0.462	0.436	0.378	0.337	0.290	1.09
13:00:55	1	"	138	0.448	0.426	0.370	0.328	0.283	1.08
13:30:17	1	"	139	0.452	0.425	0.364	0.358	0.308	1.03
13:59:55	1	"	140	0.476	0.451	0.395	0.356	0.307	1.06
14:29:51	1	"	141	0.493	0.465	0.415	0.378	0.324	1.04
15:00:07	1	"	142	0.483	0.457	0.404	0.391	0.337	0.96
15:30:14	1	"	143	0.461	0.439	0.390	0.394	0.315	0.96
16:00:16	1	"	144	0.467	0.422	0.368	0.339	0.292	0.96
16:30:42			145	0.457	0.427	0.365	0.338	0.291	0.94

SKY CONDITIONS: [0] Clear Sky; [1] Haze; [2] Thin cirrus-sun not obscured; [3] Thin cirrus - sun obscured;
 [4] Scattered cumulus - sun not obscured; [5] Cumulus over most of the sky - sun not obscured;
 [6] Cumulus - sun obscured; [7] complete cumulus cover; [8] Status- sub obscured; [9] Drizzle.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 166

Date: 1st February 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	N		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	N
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	Y
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	Y

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B166

Date: 1st February 2006

Instruments

1. JW – not operated
2. Upper Pyrgeometer – signal and zero noisy
3. FFC window very mucky!
4. Mission Scientist's Laptop display locked up – rebooted then okay
5. Flight Manager's Laptop display locked up – rebooted then okay
6. Ozone noisy in flight possibly temperature related. Switched it off at 151120 for ~15 minutes. Switched back on then okay. (Also possible lag in signal).

Cloud Physics – PCASP ok

FFSSP- switched off at low level,

2DC – ok

SID 2 noisy on occasions, otherwise ok

AMS & PAN – excellent!

Wet Neph – Zero out of calibration

IR Camera – not operated

CCN, CVI, SWS, VACC – ok

SHIMS – initialisation problems in flight, possibly temperature related. Powered down for a while then okay.

Bags - ~40 bags filled and 12 tubes

Not fitted: ARIES, MARSS, DEIMOS

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom H Calls - Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B166:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics In Flight	
Cloud Physics Processing	
PSAP	
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
VACC	No log is taken/provided for VACC

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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